

CHANGES IN CHOLESTEROL METABOLISM IN PERIPHERAL CELLS OF ALZHEIMER DISEASE PATIENTS AND THEIR RELATIVES

Alessandra Pani ^a, Paolo La Colla ^a, Claudia Abete ^a, Claudia Mulas ^a, Marirosa Putzolu ^a, Claudia Norfo ^a, Sergio Laconi ^a, Anna Borgia ^b, Cristina Zaru ^{ac}, Manuela Palmas ^{ac}, Paolo F. Putzu ^c, Alessandra Mocali ^d, Francesco Paoletti ^d and Sandra Dessì ^a

^aDepartment of Biomedical Sciences and Technologies, University of Cagliari,

^bBlood Transfusion Center, ASL7, Iglesias, ^cAlzheimer Center, ASL8, Cagliari and

^dDepartment of Experimental Pathology and Oncology, University of Florence, Italy

ABSTRACT

Background. Previous epidemiological and experimental studies indicated cholesterol as a central player in Alzheimer disease (AD). Here, we utilized skin fibroblasts and PBMC as possible ex vivo models for the study of dysfunctions of cholesterol homeostasis which may be related to AD development.

Methods. We analyzed cholesterol homeostasis using colorimetric, thin layer chromatography (TLC), and histologic technique in ex vivo cultures of skin fibroblasts and PBMCs from patients with probable AD and their first-degree relatives. Additionally, healthy age-matched individuals served as controls.

Findings. As compared to controls, skin fibroblasts and PBMCs from AD patients, displayed an evident alteration of cholesterol metabolism; namely an anomalous accumulation of cholesterol esters in their cytoplasm. No change in intracellular free cholesterol was observed. Cellular overloading of cholesterol esters was dramatically increased after specific growth stimulation of the different cell types. Cholesterol ester accumulation was negatively correlated to plasma levels of high density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) and positively correlated with severity of cognitive symptoms measured by Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE). Inhibitors of cholesterol esterification, such as progesterone and SaH, as well as a potent inhibitor of cell proliferation, RAD, were able to prevent accumulation of cholesterol esters.

Interpretation. Changes of cholesterol esters in the peripheral compartment may be indicative of a systemic alteration of intracellular cholesterol homeostasis, which in turn might create a cellular milieu favourable to the production of β -amyloid in the brain. Pathways that control cholesterol esterification might represent promising targets for novel diagnostic and therapeutic AD approaches.

INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized by progressive deterioration of memory and cognition. Neural damage is thought to result from deposition of β -amyloid peptide ($A\beta$), a low molecular weight fragment derived from the amyloid precursor protein (APP) after proteolytic cleavage by the β -secretases. ^{1,2}

and 3. Many studies over the last decade have provided a mass of information about structural and biochemical co-factors favouring A β deposition in AD patients.⁴ Particular attention has been devoted to changes in cholesterol metabolism.^{5, 6,7 and 8} However, these studies carried out in animal models or in cell culture systems have often yielded conflicting results. Several “in vitro” studies have reported a reduced secretion of A β in cells that have been depleted of cholesterol^{4,6,9}. In line with these findings some, “in vivo” studies have shown that an environment low in cholesterol favours the production of the non-amyloidogenic, soluble fragments of (α APPs).^{9,10} On the basis of such findings it has been suggested that a high cholesterol content in rafts, where β -secretases are located, could promote the co-clustering of these enzymes and APP, thereby promoting the production of APP-derived amyloidogenic cleavage fragments. However, contrasting with this picture, some “in vivo” evidence would indicate that low brain cholesterol levels can in fact promote AD development.¹¹ Moreover, some clinical evidence does not support the notion that high brain cholesterol levels are associated with AD development. In fact, a reduction rather than an increase in membrane cholesterol was observed in the hippocampus of AD patients by Ledesma and collaborators¹², while Abad-Rodriguez and collaborators,¹³ demonstrated that a reduction of membrane cholesterol in hippocampal neurons from AD patients resulted in a higher β -secretase –APP co-localization in rafts associated with an elevated production of A β . Since a comprehensive view of the complex relationship between cholesterol metabolism and AD is still lacking, it is difficult, at present, to reconcile all these conflicting reports. However, it is reasonable to suggest that, similarly to other metabolic and biochemical alterations found in AD patients, alterations in cholesterol metabolism, rather than being confined to the brain tissue, might be systemic in AD patients. Indeed, a number of abnormalities in metabolic and biochemical processes described in AD brains have also been found in cultured skin fibroblasts derived from AD patients,^{14,15} thus supporting the view that AD might be seen as a systemic disorder and that fibroblasts and other peripheral cells might be useful to identify and to test hypotheses on brain pathological mechanisms leading to AD. Starting from these considerations, in the present work we investigated cholesterol metabolism in skin fibroblasts and in peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) from AD patients and their first-degree relatives as possible ex vivo models for the identification of alterations in cholesterol homeostatic regulatory pathways that may be relevant to AD development and progression.

METHODS

Participants. In a first phase of study, we took advantage of a pre-existing bank of skin fibroblasts collected as part of a project of "Ricerca Finalizzata Alzheimer", funded by the Ministero della Salute through Regione Toscana and entitled "Identification and validation of peripheral markers of altered proteolysis in AD patients. All individuals included in this study were enrolled at the Azienda USL 4, Geriatric Unit of Prato Hospital (Italy). The dermal biopsies were obtained, following informed written

consent, from the upper forearm of the subjects by a 2-mm punch after local anesthesia with 2% xylocaine, according to the guidelines established and approved by the local Ethical Committee of Azienda USL 4, Prato (Italy). We analysed fibroblasts from six non-AD controls (six females, mean age 67.0 ± 6.1 years) and seven AD patients (five females, two males, mean age 73.8 ± 9.4 years). In a second phase, blood samples were obtained from 62 patients with probable AD (range: 64–91 years; mean \pm S.E. = 78.6 ± 0.8), predominantly women (49/62) and from 78 first-degree relatives (range: 26–87 years; mean \pm S.E. = 47.0 ± 1.3) (55/78 women), recruited at the Geriatric Service of Alzheimer Center, USL 8, Cagliari (Italy). Informed written consent was obtained from all the subjects or, when necessary, from their legal guardians under local institutional review board supervision and approval (# 351, 14 Feb 2003) of local Ethical Committee of USL 8, Cagliari, Italy. Routine clinical and laboratory evaluation, including magnetic resonance imaging, was performed to exclude other causes of cognitive impairment. The Reisberg Global Deterioration Scale (GDS) was used to indicate the severity of the cognitive impairment in AD patients. Abnormal GDS levels start from level 3 and maximal deterioration grade corresponds to level 7. Patient evaluation included medical history, physical and neurological examinations, laboratory blood tests to rule out metabolic causes of dementia (thyroid hormones, Vitamin B12, and erythrocyte sedimentation rate), and a neuroimaging (computed tomography and/or magnetic resonance) of the brain. In addition, all patients received neuropsychological tests including the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) (mean \pm S.E. = 18.9 ± 0.5). Patients with neoplastic or hematological disorders, recent infections or surgery, severe hepatic or renal failure, myocardial infarction or cranial trauma in the previous 6 months, or who had received statins, antineoplastic, corticosteroid, or immunosuppressive drug treatments were not included in the present study. Additionally, 114 individuals: 30 volunteers aged between 65–87 years (22/30 women) with no cognitive impairment, as determined by clinical interview and by a normal MMSE score (29.4 ± 0.6) and 84 blood donors, recruited at the Centro Trasfusionale, USL7, Iglesias, Italy, (35/84 women) aged between 19 and 69 years; mean \pm S.E. = 42.5 ± 1.3 , with no personal or family history of neurological or psychiatric disorders, served as controls.

Cell cultures. Skin fibroblasts were isolated by dermal biopsies obtained from the upper forearm by a 2-mm punch after local anesthesia with 2% xylocaine. Biopsies were washed with sterile PBS supplemented with penicillin and streptomycin, minced to pieces, transferred to culture dishes and overlaid with a coverslip. Cultures were incubated at 37°C in 5% CO_2 humidified atmosphere with DMEM containing 4.5 g/l glucose and 10% FCS for 18–21 days to obtain primary cultures of human diploid fibroblasts. These were then subcultured, seeded onto 60-mm plastic Petri dishes (28 cm^2) in 10% FCS–DMEM and grown to confluence. All experiments were completed using fibroblasts between passages two to three in culture. For “in vitro” kinetic experiments, cells were plated at a density of $10,000\text{ cell/cm}^2$ in 6 well plates and then incubated for 48 h in DMEM with 0.2% FCS to synchronize cells at a quiescent state. Quiescent fibroblasts were then diluted in complete growth medium

with 10% FCS, either in the presence or in the absence of 20 nM of 40-O-(2-hydroxyethyl) rapamycin (RAD) (supplied by Novartis Pharma AG, Basel, Switzerland). In addition, 10 μ M of Progesterone (PG) (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO) and 4 μ M of the acyl amide ACAT inhibitor SaH (Novartis Pharma AG, Basel) was added to some cultures as a broad-spectrum regulators of cholesterol ester cycle. Preliminary experiments were carried out to find the minimal effective dosages with the least effect on cell viability. Cells were harvested at indicated time points after treatments. Cell proliferation was assessed by direct cell counting with a hemocytometer. The trypan blue exclusion test was used to assess cell viability.

Blood samples. Blood samples were centrifuged at 2200 rpm for 15 min to separate plasma. Plasma was removed, transferred to centrifuge tubes and stored at -80°C until analyses. The buffy coat was collected and the peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were isolated by density-gradient centrifugation (Lymphoprep; density, 1.077 g/L; Nycomed Pharma, Oslo, Norway) at 1200 rpm for 10 minutes at 20°C , and washed twice with Hanks balanced salt solution (HBSS). Purified PBMCs were then seeded onto 24-well plates at $1.0 \times 10^6/\text{mL}$ in RPMI 1640 medium with the standard supplements: (10% fetal calf serum (FCS), 200 mM L-glutamine, and 100 U/mL penicillin-streptomycin) and, where indicated, growth-stimulated with 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ phytohemagglutinin (PHA; Sigma) in the presence or in the absence of 20 nM of RAD.

Plasma lipid profile. Total (TC) and HDL cholesterol (HDL-C) content was determined in plasma by routine colorimetric enzymatic procedures (Sclavo Diagnostics International S.r.l. Sovicille, Italy).

Cholesterol esterification and lipid cell content. Cholesterol esterification was evaluated by incubating cells for 6 hours in medium containing [$1-^{14}\text{C}$]oleic acid (Dupont, NEN 55 mCi/mmol), bound to bovine serum albumin (BSA) at a final concentration of 2 $\mu\text{Ci}/\text{ml}$. After incubation cells were washed with PBS and lipids extracted with acetone. Lipid subclasses were separated by thin layer chromatography (TLC) and incorporation of [^{14}C]oleate into cholesterol esters was measured. For lipid cell content determinations, free (FC) and esterified cholesterol (CE) were separated by TLC and their mass determined by enzymatic assay methods.

Neutral lipid staining. To visualize the degree of cytoplasmic neutral lipid accumulation, cultured fibroblasts and freshly isolated PBMCs were washed three times with PBS and fixed by soaking in 10% formalin. Cells were then treated with isopropyl alcohol (60%), washed, stained with oil red O (ORO) (a lipid-soluble dye that stains cholesterol esters but not free cholesterol) and counterstained with Mayer's hematoxylin. Stained cells were examined by light microscopy and digital images were recorded. For quantification of mean neutral lipid content in skin fibroblasts, red color intensity was measured in single cells using the software Scion Image (Scion Corp., Fredrick, Maryland, USA). Values were expressed as the mean of red color intensity in each cell, determined in at least 30 single cells in six random microscopic fields. Neutral lipids in ORO stained PBMCs calculated as above were further graded into 5

classes: 0 (0), 1 (+), 2 (++) , 3 (+++) and 4 (++++) based on mean color intensity measurements.

Statistical analysis. Data are reported as mean \pm standard error (SE). Statistical calculations were performed using the statistical analysis software of Origin 7.0 version (Microcal, Inc, Northampton, MA, USA). A value of $P < 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant. Correlation analysis were performed by correlation test of Microsoft Excel for Statistics.

Funding source. This study was supported by grants of Regione Autonoma della Sardegna and of Monte dei Paschi di Siena.

RESULTS

A number of abnormalities in metabolic and biochemical processes described in AD brains have been found in cultured skin fibroblasts derived from AD patients.^{14,15} Prompted by our previous findings of a tight correlation between cell growth and cholesterol ester accumulation^{16,17,18} and ²⁰ in various cell systems and by studies demonstrating abnormally high levels of intracellular lipid droplets (mainly cholesterol esters) in cell-based and animal models of AD ^{21, 22, 23, and 24}, we initially sought to explore a possible relationship between growth capability and the extent of cholesterol esterification in skin fibroblasts obtained from AD patients (AD fibroblasts). Direct cell counting revealed a significantly higher mytogenic response of AD fibroblasts as compared to control fibroblasts 72 hours after 10% FCS stimulation (5×10^6 vs. 3×10^6 cells/ml). As expected, the increase in cell number correlated with a parallel increase in the rate of cholesterol esterification (data not shown). Noteworthy, total cholesterol was significantly higher in AD fibroblasts as compared to controls ($59,3 \pm 2.0$ μg cholesterol/mg cell protein vs. 45.0 ± 1.5 μg cholesterol/mg cell protein); this increment was mainly accounted by an increased CE content in AD fibroblasts and resulted in a striking decrease in the FC /CE ratio in these cells (2.5 ± 0.3 , vs 11.2 ± 1.2). Analysis by ORO staining revealed that unstimulated control fibroblasts contain very low basal levels of cytoplasmic neutral lipid droplets (figure 1), confirming that, under normal conditions, intracellular cholesterol esters are maintained at low levels, possibly by a cyclic process of de-esterification and re-esterification, as originally suggested by Goldstein and Brown ²⁵. On the other hand, ORO staining of AD-fibroblasts confirmed that this regulatory mechanism is altered in AD patients, as evidenced by the greatly expanded cytoplasmic CE pool in these cells (figure 1 A and B). Moreover, the finding that, three different inhibitors of cholesterol esterification were able to reduce lipid droplet accumulation in AD fibroblasts (figure 1B) constitutes a strong evidence that this expanded CE pool is, at least partly, due to an increased esterification activity. Taken together, these results suggest that the mechanism(s) involved in the regulation of cholesterol esterification may be systemically altered in AD-patients.

Figure 1. Neutral lipids in fibroblasts from controls and AD patients. The upper panel (A) shows analysis of ORO-stainings performed on six controls and seven AD different fibroblast cell cultures. Bars indicate the mean \pm SE of red color intensity/cell, determined in each culture well in at least 30 single cells in six random microscopic fields. $*p < 0.05$ vs. control values. Panel B shows lipid droplet accumulation in 48 hours FCS stimulated AD fibroblasts incubated in the presence or in the absence of SaH, PG, and RAD. Shown are results from 1 control and 1 AD patient which are representative of six controls and seven AD different fibroblast cell lines.

If this hypothesis is correct, than at least in theory, one should expect that this systemic alteration could also be reflected by changes of lipid levels in the plasma. To test such a possibility we thus studied TC and HDL-C levels in plasma and neutral lipid content in PBMCs from 62 patients with probable AD as well as from 30 age-matched healthy controls. Levels of TC were moderately decreased in the plasma from AD patients as compared to controls but this was not statistically significant. By contrast, plasma HDL-C levels were significantly decreased, in AD patients

(figure 2A) as compared to controls. This paralleled with increased levels of CE in AD-PBMCs (figure 2B) indicating that abnormally low levels of HDL-C coupled with cytoplasmic accumulation of CE might be relevant in AD pathogenesis.

If examined individually, the majority of AD-PBMCs (53%) had ORO staining levels (calculated as stated in Methods) that scored between 3 and 4, while the majority of PBMCs from controls (58 %) scored between 0 and 1 (figure 3A). In addition, correlation test revealed that in AD patients, ORO staining levels in PBMCs were negatively correlated with HDL-C levels in plasma ($r=-0.44$, $P < 0.05$) (figure 3B).

Although the significance, if any, of observed correlation between low HDL-C levels and AD risk remains to be established, the data presented above lead to suggest that the low HDL-C levels in the plasma of AD patients may be a consequence of a decreased removal rate of cholesterol from tissues, possibly as a result of the increased rate of cholesterol esterification and intracellular lipid droplet accumulation. Interestingly, the intensity of ORO staining in PBMCs of AD was significantly and directly correlated with the severity of cognitive alteration, determined by the MMSE scores ($r = -0.41$; $p < 0.05$) (figure 3 C). This last finding would suggest that, rather than being just an epiphenomenon, this metabolic alteration might have some clinical relevance and/or perhaps contribute to the pathogenesis of this disease.

Figure 2. Plasma cholesterol and neutral lipids in PBMCs from AD patients (AD-PBMCs). Panel A shows TC and HDL-C in plasma of 62 AD patients and 30 age-matched controls. * $P < 0.05$ vs controls. Panel B shows neutral lipid droplet accumulation as determined by ORO method in quiescent (0h) and 48 hours PHA stimulated AD-PBMCs incubated in the presence or in the absence of RAD.

Figure 3. Correlation between neutral lipid in PBMCs and HDL-C levels in plasma. Panel A. Numbers of control and AD blood samples, distributed according to the intensity of the ORO bound lipids, and sub-divided into five classes: (0), 1(+), 2 (++) , 3 (+++) and 4 (++++) based on intensity measurements. Panel B Correlations between HDL-C and ORO intensity in AD and age-matched controls. Panel C Correlations between MMSE scores and ORO intensity in AD and age-matched controls.

It is well known that individuals who have had a late onset-AD case in their family may run an increased risk of developing AD themselves.²⁶ However, with the exception of apolipoprotein E polymorphisms,²⁷ and ²⁸ no accepted indicator is so far available to estimate risk in AD relatives. It will be thus worth investigating whether altered cholesterol metabolic profile might serve for the pre-clinical identification of a subset of AD relatives who might be at major risk of developing AD later in their lifetime. We therefore studied HDL-C levels in plasma and the content of ORO lipid droplets in PBMCs in 78 first-degree relatives of AD patients and compared the data with those obtained from 84 age-matched healthy controls. When compared to both the AD and control groups, a greater variability was observed in the data obtained from first-degree AD relatives (mean age: 47.0 ± 1.3), and a partial overlap was present with the data from a control group (mean age: 42.5 ± 1.3) (figure 4A). However, 41% of PBMCs from AD relatives had ORO staining levels that scored between 2 and 3, as compared to only 18% of PBMCs from controls (Figure 4B).

Figure 4. Correlation between neutral lipid in PBMCs and HDL-C levels in plasma of first degree relatives of AD patients. Panel A. Total and HDL-C levels. Panel B. Numbers of control and AD first degree relatives blood samples, distributed according to the intensity of the ORO bound lipids, and sub-divided into five classes: (0), 1(+), 2 (++) , 3 (+++) and 4 (++++) based

on intensity measurements. Panel C. Correlations between HDL-C and ORO intensity in AD first degree relatives and age-matched controls.

In addition, similarly to what observed in AD patients, plasma HDL-C levels were significantly correlated with ORO intensity ($r=-0.39$, $P< 0.05$) in AD relatives (figure 4C), indicating that some AD relatives tend to display a cholesterol metabolic pattern similar to that of typical AD patients. Interestingly, three unaffected relatives (two brothers and 1 sister) of comparable age of three AD patients did not show relevant accumulation of neutral lipid in their PBMCs (figure 5).

Figure 5. Comparison of ORO staining between three AD patients and three unaffected relatives (two brothers and 1 sister) of comparable age.

DISCUSSION

Many experimental and clinical studies indicate that cholesterol plays a role in AD^{1,5, 23}. The exact nature of this role, however, remains elusive, since available data are often conflicting and in most studies no information on intracellular cholesterol pools (free vs. esterified) and/or lipoprotein fractions was available. High levels of total plasma cholesterol have been variably associated with either increased^{7,29,30 and 31} or decreased²⁹ risk of AD, while other studies have found no association at all. Early work that served as a rationale for the use of statins as novel “quick and easy” therapy for AD³², had to be entirely re-examined when three independent prospective studies, altogether accounting for about 30,000 person-years at risk for AD, found no protective effect of statins against AD development. The rationale to the use of statins in AD was based on the hypothesis that high cholesterol levels accelerate the production of β -amyloid by shifting APP metabolism from alpha to beta cleavage products. According to this hypothesis, statins, blocking cholesterol synthesis, would cause a reduction in neuronal membrane free-cholesterol content, thus inhibiting the activity of β -secretases. While this theoretical arguments were initially supported by some in vitro observations, a recent epidemiological study found that statins use was associated with a greater risk of AD.³³ To explain this surprising result, the authors of this study have suggested that

statins might exacerbate AD progression by inhibiting cholesterol synthesis at the neuronal level, thus altering cholesterol-dependent synaptic integrity and neurotransmission. In an attempt to understand the reasons for these apparently conflicting reports and to have a larger view of the relationship between cholesterol and AD, in the present study we investigated and compared the overall cholesterol metabolism in patients with probable AD and age-matched healthy controls. We evaluated lipid profiles in the plasma compartment as well as intracellular cholesterol pools in skin fibroblasts and/or PBMCs. Unlike fibroblasts and PBMCs from controls, which were virtually devoid of lipid droplets, cells from AD patients accumulated a large number of lipid droplets (mainly cholesterol esters). This accumulation was associated with lower levels of plasma HDL-C, while no change in plasma TC levels was observed between AD patients and age-matched controls. Interestingly, the extent of neutral lipid accumulation in cells was inversely correlated with HDL-C levels in plasma. The combination of low plasma HDL-C and cellular lipid accumulation is intriguing in the light of the proposed role of HDL in unloading cholesterol from tissues, including brain, and transporting it back to the liver. In this respect, low HDL-C levels would seem to indicate that lipid export from cells is defective in AD patients, possibly leading to increased amounts of cholesterol ester storage in the cytoplasm. This view is corroborated by studies showing that HDL-C and ApoA-I (the main apolipoprotein of HDL) levels, are significantly lower in the plasma of AD patients in comparison to the controls^{34,35} and that deficiency in ATP-binding cassette ABCA1³⁶, the major regulator of cholesterol efflux, increases β -amyloid deposition. Low HDL-C levels in plasma and a reduction of LDL receptor expression in PBMC were also found in Down syndrome patients which, in spite of high risk for AD, show a low prevalence of coronary artery disease.³⁷

In the present study we found that skin fibroblasts from AD patients, although showing a normal content of free cholesterol, display an evident alteration of cholesterol metabolism; namely an anomalous accumulation of cholesterol esters in their cytoplasm. This intracellular overloading with cholesterol esters was dramatically increased after mitogenic stimulation, while two different inhibitors of cholesterol esterification, such as progesterone and SaH, as well as a potent inhibitor of cell proliferation, RAD, were able to prevent it. We hypothesize that these observed changes in cholesterol esters in the peripheral compartment may be indicative of a systemic alteration of intracellular cholesterol homeostasis, which in turn might create a cellular milieu favourable to the production of β -amyloid in the brain.

In agreement with this hypothesis, Kovacs et al. found that cholesterol-ester levels are directly correlated to A β production: a decrease in the content of lipid droplets led to a decrease in the production of A β , whereas abnormally high levels of lipid droplets led to an increase in amyloid beta production.^{21,24} The Authors also showed that drugs known to inhibit the activity of acyl-coenzyme A:cholesterol acyltransferase (ACAT), the enzyme that catalyses the formation of cholesterol esters, are potent modulators of A β generation^{21,24}. Moreover, a RNAi-induced, 50% reduction of ACAT expression resulted in a significant suppression of A β production (\sim 40%) confirming that

reduction of cellular ACAT activity represents a realistic and specific approach for the modulation of $A\beta$ generation. Therefore, inhibitors of this enzyme may turn out to be an extremely important tool in the treatment of AD.²²

Another interesting finding of our study was that neutral lipid accumulation in PBMCs correlated positively with the severity of dementia, expressed by the MMSE score. These observations not only indicate that a progressive systemic alteration in cholesterol metabolism accompanies the development of mental deterioration, thus implying measurements of neutral lipids in peripheral cells, together with HDL-C in plasma, may be useful in the monitoring of AD progression, but also suggests that assessment of cholesterol metabolisms in peripheral cells among asymptomatic AD relatives might serve to identify those that carry a higher risk of developing the disease at older ages. To our knowledge, these findings are the first *ex vivo* demonstration that alterations of cholesterol metabolism, which are associated with AD and parallel disease severity, are also present in peripheral cells, and support biochemical, epidemiological, and genetic literature arguing for a deep link between cholesterol and AD.^{1,5,23} Focusing on the relationship between cholesterol and APP metabolism would be important for etiological as well as for therapeutic purposes, as it might help to understand whether early pharmacological interventions on cholesterol levels could provide a relatively safe mean to reduce $A\beta$ accumulation both in brain and in endothelial compartment. These data confirm that new therapeutic approaches targeting lipid metabolism may be useful to slow down AD progression.

In summary, further studies are necessary to elucidate the mechanisms responsible for the alterations of cholesterol homeostasis in AD patients and in their first degree relatives, and to unveil possible cause-effect relationships between APP cleavage and these alterations. Similarly, additional work is needed to fully explore the potential implication of this association for AD susceptibility. Nonetheless, the data reported in the present paper suggest that accumulation of cholesterol esters in peripheral cells, together with a decrease of HDL-C in the plasma might serve to identify a distinctive profile associated with increased susceptibility to AD. In addition, the lack of an AD diagnostic has limited so far the development of specific drugs and the assessment of the response of peripheral tissues to disease-modifying therapies. Fibroblasts and/or PBMCs from AD patients could represent an excellent *in vitro* model to test the toxicity as well as the efficacy of agents capable of restoring the control of cholesterol homeostasis toward the profile of the normal phenotype.

Acknowledgements. The Authors thank volunteers, blood donors and AD patient relatives that with enthusiasm have accepted to participate to this study. Appreciation is extended to Anna Saba and Martina Ciuffo for technical assistance.

REFERENCES

1. Govaerts L, Schoenen J, Bouhy D. [Pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease: molecular and cellular mechanisms]. *Rev Med Liege*. 2007 Apr;62(4):209-16.

2. John V. Human beta-secretase (BACE) and BACE inhibitors: progress report. *Curr Top Med Chem.* 2006;6(6):569-78.
3. Stockley JH, O'Neill C. The proteins BACE1 and BACE2 and beta-secretase activity in normal and Alzheimer's disease brain. *Biochem Soc Trans.* 2007 Jun;35(Pt 3):574-6.
4. Haass C, Selkoe DJ. Cellular processing of beta-amyloid precursor protein and the genesis of amyloid beta-peptide. *Cell.* 1993 Dec 17;75(6):1039-42.
5. Frears ER, Stephens DJ, Walters CE, Davies H, Austen BM. The role of cholesterol in the biosynthesis of beta-amyloid. *Neuroreport.* 1999 Jun 3;10(8):1699-705.
6. Galbete JL, Martin TR, Peressini E, Modena P, Bianchi R, Forloni G. Cholesterol decreases secretion of the secreted form of amyloid precursor protein by interfering with glycosylation in the protein secretory pathway. *Biochem J.* 2000 Jun 1;348 Pt 2:307-13.
7. Notkola IL, Sulkava R, Pekkanen J, Erkinjuntti T, Ehnholm C, Kivinen P, et al. Serum total cholesterol, apolipoprotein E epsilon 4 allele, and Alzheimer's disease. *Neuroepidemiology.* 1998;17(1):14-20.
8. Refolo LM, Pappolla MA, LaFrancois J, Malester B, Schmidt SD, Thomas-Bryant T, et al. A cholesterol-lowering drug reduces beta-amyloid pathology in a transgenic mouse model of Alzheimer's disease. *Neurobiol Dis.* 2001 Oct;8(5):890-9.
9. Kojro E, Gimpl G, Lammich S, Marz W, Fahrenholz F. Low cholesterol stimulates the nonamyloidogenic pathway by its effect on the alpha -secretase ADAM 10. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 2001 May 8;98(10):5815-20.
10. Simons M, Keller P, De Strooper B, Beyreuther K, Dotti CG, Simons K. Cholesterol depletion inhibits the generation of beta-amyloid in hippocampal neurons. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 1998 May 26;95(11):6460-4.
11. Park IH, Hwang EM, Hong HS, Boo JH, Oh SS, Lee J, et al. Lovastatin enhances Abeta production and senile plaque deposition in female Tg2576 mice. *Neurobiol Aging.* 2003 Sep;24(5):637-43.
12. Ledesma MD, Abad-Rodriguez J, Galvan C, Biondi E, Navarro P, Delacourte A, et al. Raft disorganization leads to reduced plasmin activity in Alzheimer's disease brains. *EMBO Rep.* 2003 Dec;4(12):1190-6.
13. Abad-Rodriguez J, Ledesma MD, Craessaerts K, Perga S, Medina M, Delacourte A, et al. Neuronal membrane cholesterol loss enhances amyloid peptide generation. *J Cell Biol.* 2004 Dec 6;167(5):953-60.
14. Gasparini L, Racchi M, Binetti G, Trabucchi M, Solerte SB, Alkon D, et al. Peripheral markers in testing pathophysiological hypotheses and diagnosing Alzheimer's disease. *FASEB J.* 1998 Jan;12(1):17-34.
15. Govoni S, Gasparini L, Racchi M, Trabucchi M. Peripheral cells as an investigational tool for Alzheimer's disease. *Life Sci.* 1996;59(5-6):461-8.
16. Batetta B, Bonatesta RR, Sanna F, Putzolu M, Mulas MF, Collu M, et al. Cell growth and cholesterol metabolism in human glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficient lymphomononuclear cells. *Cell Prolif.* 2002 Jun;35(3):143-54.

17. Batetta B, Dessi S, Putzolu M, Sanna F, Spano O, Mulas MF, et al. MDR1 gene expression in normal and atherosclerotic human arteries(1). *J Vasc Res.* 1999 Jul-Aug;36(4):261-71.
18. Batetta B, Mulas MF, Petruzzo P, Putzolu M, Bonatesta RR, Sanna F, et al. Opposite pattern of MDR1 and caveolin-1 gene expression in human atherosclerotic lesions and proliferating human smooth muscle cells. *Cell Mol Life Sci.* 2001 Jul;58(8):1113-20.
19. Batetta B, Mulas MF, Sanna F, Putzolu M, Bonatesta RR, Gasperi-Campani A, et al. Role of cholesterol ester pathway in the control of cell cycle in human aortic smooth muscle cells. *FASEB J.* 2003 Apr;17(6):746-8.
20. Pani A, Batetta B, Putzolu M, Sanna F, Spano O, Piras S, et al. MDR1, cholesterol certification and cell growth: a comparative study in normal and multidrug-resistant KB cell lines. *Cell Mol Life Sci.* 2000 Jul;57(7):1094-102.
21. Hutter-Paier B, Huttunen HJ, Puglielli L, Eckman CB, Kim DY, Hofmeister A, et al. The ACAT inhibitor CP-113,818 markedly reduces amyloid pathology in a mouse model of Alzheimer's disease. *Neuron.* 2004 Oct 14;44(2):227-38.
22. Huttunen HJ, Greco C, Kovacs DM. Knockdown of ACAT-1 reduces amyloidogenic processing of APP. *FEBS Lett.* 2007 Apr 17;581(8):1688-92.
23. Puglielli L, Ellis BC, Ingano LA, Kovacs DM. Role of acyl-coenzyme A: cholesterol acyltransferase activity in the processing of the amyloid precursor protein. *J Mol Neurosci.* 2004;24(1):93-6.
24. Puglielli L, Konopka G, Pack-Chung E, Ingano LA, Berezovska O, Hyman BT, et al. Acyl-coenzyme A: cholesterol acyltransferase modulates the generation of the amyloid beta-peptide. *Nat Cell Biol.* 2001 Oct;3(10):905-12.
25. Brown MS, Goldstein JL. Lipoprotein metabolism in the macrophage: implications for cholesterol deposition in atherosclerosis. *Annu Rev Biochem.* 1983;52:223-61.
26. Silverman JM, Ciresi G, Smith CJ, Marin DB, Schnaider-Beerl M. Variability of familial risk of Alzheimer disease across the late life span. *Arch Gen Psychiatry.* 2005 May;62(5):565-73.
27. Corder EH, Saunders AM, Strittmatter WJ, Schmechel DE, Gaskell PC, Small GW, et al. Gene dose of apolipoprotein E type 4 allele and the risk of Alzheimer's disease in late onset families. *Science.* 1993 Aug 13;261(5123):921-3.
28. Roses AD. Apolipoprotein E alleles as risk factors in Alzheimer's disease. *Annu Rev Med.* 1996;47:387-400.
29. Michikawa M. Cholesterol paradox: is high total or low HDL cholesterol level a risk for Alzheimer's disease? *J Neurosci Res.* 2003 Apr 15;72(2):141-6.
30. Pappolla MA, Bryant-Thomas TK, Herbert D, Pacheco J, Fabra Garcia M, Manjon M, et al. Mild hypercholesterolemia is an early risk factor for the development of Alzheimer amyloid pathology. *Neurology.* 2003 Jul 22;61(2):199-205.
31. Tan ZS, Seshadri S, Beiser A, Wilson PW, Kiel DP, Tocco M, et al. Plasma total cholesterol level as a risk factor for Alzheimer disease: the Framingham Study. *Arch Intern Med.* 2003 May 12;163(9):1053-7.

32. Jick H, Zornberg GL, Jick SS, Seshadri S, Drachman DA. Statins and the risk of dementia. *Lancet*. 2000 Nov 11;356(9242):1627-31.
33. Rea TD, Breitner JC, Psaty BM, Fitzpatrick AL, Lopez OL, Newman AB, et al. Statin use and the risk of incident dementia: the Cardiovascular Health Study. *Arch Neurol*. 2005 Jul;62(7):1047-51.
34. Liu HC, Hu CJ, Chang JG, Sung SM, Lee LS, Yuan RY, et al. Proteomic identification of lower apolipoprotein A-I in Alzheimer's disease. *Dement Geriatr Cogn Disord*. 2006;21(3):155-61.
35. Merched A, Xia Y, Visvikis S, Serot JM, Siest G. Decreased high-density lipoprotein cholesterol and serum apolipoprotein AI concentrations are highly correlated with the severity of Alzheimer's disease. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2000 Jan-Feb;21(1):27-30.
36. Wollmer MA, Streffer JR, Lutjohann D, Tsolaki M, Iakovidou V, Hegi T, et al. ABCA1 modulates CSF cholesterol levels and influences the age at onset of Alzheimer's disease. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2003 May-Jun;24(3):421-6.
37. Corsi MM, Malavazos AE, Passoni D, Licastro F. LDL receptor expression on T lymphocytes in old patients with Down syndrome. *Immun Ageing*. 2005 Feb 10;2(1):3.